

Porosity Measurement in Buffalo Tooth

Paper ID: 21437 | Submission Date: 2026-04-09 | Acceptance Date: 2026-04-21 | Publication Date: 2026-04-25

This is an open-access research article distributed under the terms of the **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License**, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are properly credited.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20488757

For verification of this paper, please visit:

<http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/anthology.php#8>

Sandeep Kumar
Assistant Professor
Dept. Of Physics
J.V. Jain College
Saharanpur, U.P., India

Vakul Bansal
Principal
J.V. Jain College
Saharanpur
U.P., India

Abstract

The teeth are one of the most useful part of the body. Premature loss of any tooth may cause a collapse of the dental arch and movement of individual teeth and hence Dentists are in search of better treatment techniques for dental diseases. Porosity is a very important technique for the determination of structure of solid and for distinction from amorphous to crystalline states. The present research article deals with porosity study of teeth for understanding the hardness of different teeth.

Keywords

Porosity Measurement, Teeth, Root, Jaw.

Introduction

Teeth are an important part of the human system. Most of the people lose their teeth at a young age due to some disease like stomach ache and indigestion problems. Teeth form a part of the masticatory apparatus and are fixed to the jaw. Each tooth has three parts:

- (a) Crown, projecting above the gum
- (b) Root embedded in the jaw beneath the gum, and
- (c) Neck between the crown and the root surrounded by the gum.

Each tooth is composed of:

1. Pulp in the center, which is a loose fibrous tissue
2. Dentine surrounding the pulp, which is a calcified material containing spiral tubules radiating from the pulp cavity
3. Enamel as the hardest animal substance by existence with 97% calcium
4. Cementum, which resembles bone in structure but like enamel and dentine it has no blood supply nor any nerve supply.
5. Periodontal membrane, which holds the root in the socket.

Objective of study

The human teeth and buffalo teeth are required to be studied analytically to understand tooth structure and the hardness of different teeth. Microscopic property of human teeth by using scanning electro microscopy have been studied measurement of physical parameter like porosity that is empty space in the tooth sample also micro hardness and density of tooth sample measured. By measuring the empty space inside the teeth we can say that which is hardest.

Review of Literature

Teeth are highly mineralized structure composed enamel, dentine, pulp, cementum, periodontal, membrane porosity of teeth refers to the presence of empty space inside the teeth. In case of buffalo teeth porosity plays an important role to determined that which one is the hardest teeth and also we can determined the mechanical strength. It is already invented that in case of buffalo enamel teeth has lower permeability than dentine teeth. Ultrasonic study of teeth has been carried out by using a double probe method through transmission technique. With the help of ultrasonic study we can compare between normal and disease teeth.

Methodology

Fifteen buffalo teeth samples were collected from slaughter houses of Saharanpur and Delhi and were used in the present study. These samples were machined in order to make their faces flat and parallel. This required in order to achieve better porosity experiment and to facilitate contact with the front faces of transducers. The teeth were allowed to dry for 30 days before machining, but were then immersed in saline liquid. The samples become flat with the help of a double wheel grinder (1420 rpm) used at the Department of Material Science, Indian Institute of Technology Roorkee. The porosity measurement was carried out using a Reichert Sung's

machine used at the Department of Material Science, Indian Institute of Technology Roorkee as shown in figure 1.

Fig. 1 (Reichert Jung machine).

Result and Discussion

As in small gold castings, porosities can result from solidification shrinkage and evolution of dissolved gases during solidification of the alloy. However, shrinkage and gas inclusion porosity are not distinctly separate in location, since both occur in those parts of the casting that are the last to solidify. Thus, in general, the porosity will frequently be interdentalitic.

A. Central Incisor: From micrographs 2(a and b), it is evident that in buffalo central incisors are free of porosity. It is a very hard tooth as compared to other teeth.

B. Lateral Incisor: From micrograph 2 (c, d, e and f) at a magnification of 200 \times , it is evident that there is very high porosity at this magnification.

C. Canine: From micrographs 2(g, h and i), in canine teeth it is evident that it is free of porosity. It is tough like the central incisor. At greater magnification it is unaffected.

D. 1st Molar: Porosity is increase in case of lateral incisor at magnification 100 \times as shown in figure 2(j, k, l). At greater magnification it showed increased porosity (fig. 2(m).

E. 2nd molar: teeth, the porosity is increased as compared to 1st molar at magnification 100, as shown in figures 2 (m, n).

Fig. 2 (a) (Central Incisor)

Fig. 2 (b) (Central Incisor)

Fig. 2 (c) (Lateral Incisor)

Fig. 2(d) (Lateral Incisor)

Fig.2 (e) (Lateral Incisor)

Fig. 2(f) (Lateral Incisor)

Fig. 2(g) (Canine)

Fig. 2 (h) (Canine)

Conclusion

It is concluded that the porosity is different for different teeth. The porosity of canine teeth and lateral incisor zero percent almost. It is found that the Porosity of in lateral incisor 1st molar and 2nd molar are increased up to 5%. Hence, we conclude that the central incisor and canine are harder then compared to the central incisor, 1st molar and 2nd molar.

References

1. P. V. Krishna Raju, B. R. R. Verma and Mahilinga Bhat, *Periodontal Implication of Class II Restorations: Clinical and SEM Evaluation, Indian Journal of Dentistry, Vol. 7, No. 1, 21 (1996).*
2. Bhaskar, S. N., *Oral Histology and Embryology, tenth Edition (1970).*
3. *Tooth Morphology – A Text Book of Tooth.*
4. Dibart- S "Children, adolescents and periodontal diseases" Department of periodontal, Goldman school of Graduate dentistry, Boston USA J-Dent1975 March25
5. Longmore--R--B, Meral-D-A "Clinical anatomy for dentistry Churchill Livingston" New York 1985
6. Jones-G-A, Grundy-PJ *Electron Microscopy in Material.*